

Chetan Bhagat's Two States - A Sweet -Sour clash of cultures

Prof. Anuradha Shukla

Asst. Professor in Communication Skills, Bharti Vidyapeeth College of Engineering, Belpada, Navi Mumbai, (M.S.) India

Abstract

Chetan Bhagat is an Indian author, columnist and motivational speaker. He is the author of 6 bestselling novels-Five points Someone (2004), One Night@the Call Center (2005), The 3 Mistakes of My Life (2008), 2 States (2009), Revolution 2020 (2011) and Half Girlfriend (2014). All six books have remained bestsellers since their release and three have inspired Bollywood films. Bhagat's debut novel, Five Points Someone, which has been adapted into the 2008 blockbuster Bollywood movie, Three Idiots, has established his fame as an author of international repute.

Key Words: Cultures, Chetan Bhagat, Two States

Chetan Bhagat is an Indian author, columnist and motivational speaker. He is the author of 6 bestselling novels-Five points Someone (2004), One Night@the Call Center (2005), The 3 Mistakes of My Life (2008), 2 States (2009), Revolution 2020 (2011) and Half Girlfriend (2014). All six books have remained bestsellers since their release and three have inspired Bollywood films. Bhagat's debut novel, Five Points Someone, which has been adapted into the 2008 blockbuster Bollywood movie, Three Idiots, has established his fame as an author of international repute. Ranging from the romantic love story to a deplorable condition of the present educational system, he has started a crusade of eradicating the evils of society by his 'sugar coated novels.' He got the Indo-American society's the Society Young Achiever Award in 2004 and the Publisher's Recognition Award in 2005. The New York Times called Bhagat 'the biggest selling English language novelists in India's history.'¹ The famous Time Magazine has counted him in the '100 Most Influential People in The World 2

and fast company USA has listed him as one of the world's 100 most creative people in business.'³

This novel depicts how the cultural differences can create problem in the matrimonial alliances and still our society's concept about love marriages. It deals with how multicultural ground realities affect 'Generation-y.' Multiculturalism study of multiple (two or more) cultures. So, here, we are going to see a journey of gaping and bridging between Tamilian (Ananya, the heroine of the fiction) and North Indian Delhi based Punjabi boy, the hero complex love story.

The most enchanting factor of the fiction is autobiographical element which is inscribed from the real story of the author Chetan Bhagat and his wife Anusha who belong to Delhi and Tamil Nadu respectively. Another interesting element is picaresque element as it moves in Delhi, Ahmadabad, Chennai and Goa. This book is remarkable in many senses. First of all its marriage proposal that itself one of a unique wordings among many love lives: "I, Krish Malhotra, would like to propose

to all of you, will all of you marry me?" 4

He finally wins the consent of all the members of Ananya's family. This proposal is unique not only for its unique wordings that had never used before but it reflects India's in-depth culture of the bond between two families during marriage, how important family consent in love-life for airy Y-generation, it tells. Back cover of the novel the scenario is totally different when it comes to India.

"Boy loves girl. Girl loves boy. They get married. In India there are a few more steps. Boy loves girl. Girl loves boy. Girl's family has to love boy. Boy's family has to love girl. Girl's family has to love boy's family. Boy's family has to love girl's family. Girl and the boy still love each other. They get married."

Chetan Bhagat is the positive attitude mentor of present (modern) India. He has acumen of giving comic treatment to a very serious theme. Two states explores love mushrooming in an orthodox, conservative society. Here, we find love shining amidst darkness and despair. This is a novel having excellent presentation of the fights of youngistan with oldistan to get the approval for marriage. Generation gap, communication gap and cultural gap – all are amalgamated brilliantly.

Chetan Bhagat's campus novel 2 States represents the voices of the youth of emerging India. Through this medium he tries to bridge the gap between the young generation and the old generation. It begins with the academic life of the main characters of the novel, Krish and Ananya, in IIM Ahmadabad, "Ananya Swaminathan – best girl in the fresher batch." 5 Bhagat writes about the selected students of the institute in general and the

girl students in particular that the students in IIM get admission because they can solve mathematics faster than 99.9% of India's population.

"They get in because they can solve mathematics problems faster than 99.9% of India's population and crack the CAT." 6

But simply it's a matter of love. A boy can't restraint his eyes to look upon carnal beauty of a girl. That happens with Krish after seeing Ananya in the very beginning of the novel:

"Her waist-length hair rippled as she tapped the steel plate with her fingers like a famished refugee. I noticed three black threads on the back of her fair neck. Someone had decided to accessorise in the most academically-oriented B-School in the country." 7

Ananya is the perfect combination of beauty with brain. She is a bold girl. She dares to oppose the mess contractor having bad quality food to all the students. Ananya represents the voices of the youth who dare to speak what is right and what is not. But Krish is the one who accepts things blindly and knowingly. He knows that the food is tasteless but he doesn't complain against it. He simply follow the theory "live and let live."

In love Nature always fuses persons of opposite choices. This happens here also seeing the opportunity to accompany bold girl he offers her his help and takes her to a restaurant. The friendship between both of them develops very fast. Krish helps Ananya to learn Economics and at that time both of them start meeting frequently. They begin to live in the same room and take liberty with which Indian society is not custom to. Krish explains, "You put a

boy and a girl in a room for a week and add lots of boring books, and sparks are sure to fly." 8

Without doubt that he wants to give voice to the needs of the modern youth who do not believe in the traditional beliefs about virginity and chastity but only know their physical needs for love and affection. Specially, She-protagonist, Ananya represents the voices of the modern youth who believe in the complete freedom of the fair-sex. She believes in the equality of men and women. She knows her rights and does what she wants. She likes to wear shorts and smoke cigarettes. Krish proposed her and she does not deny. As happens in college life they start messaging each-other and start hanging out. Time passes by very speedily and now it is the time of placement. Both of them are offered good jobs. Both the lovers with intention decide to invite their parents for the convocation ceremony as it is very necessary in India that parents must approve your love relationship. The parents of both meet, leaving Krish's father as he was not present, disapproved each other and their all the dreams shatter. Here begins tough love journey of Krish and Ananya.

It seems both are playing Zigzag puzzle with family members ultimately with the goal to win. Sometimes they loose hope also but ultimately it becomes a success story of true love, understanding, devotion and of mental level above than caste and creed.

Bhagat has a very keen mind to criticise the common follies of the country in this novel, as in this novel very beautifully presented the Indian folly called Dowry. In North India it is a "resilient evil" and Krish

mother wants to cash him in gold and other gifts coming with the bride. She states, "I can show you Punjabi girls as fair as milk," 9 but because to get love of Ananya Krish accepts job in Chennai, in complete new environment and hostile circumstances.

Being a fiction of young love the story weaves thread of spiritualism also. Fade up from bitter relationship from his father, Krish goes into the gap of Shri Aurobindo Ashram. He meets the Guru and tries to seek his help for his restlessness in love. Here only he set him to accept his intense passion for Ananya as he was earlier failure to receive his 1st love with a professor's daughter for that his mother was also bitten by his own father. Here Krish lost his temper and fights with his father. Krish says,

"I slapped his face once, twice, then I rolled my hand "into a fist and punched his face. My father went into a state of shock, he couldn't fight back. He didn't except this : all my childhood I'd merely suffered his dominance.....It was a reaction to two decades of abuse....I punched his head until he collapsed on the floor..... my mother sat on the bed ,fighting back her emotions .We looked at each other. We were a family, but pretty much as screwed up as they comeI looked at my father and vowed never to speak to him again." 10

Bhagat in his novels does not only point his fingers at the social issues but also he does not spare the common problems the country is facing. In 2 States he reveals a fact about Indian police that everything is possible in India only if the wrong-doer has money in his hands. Krish kisses Ananya at the famous Marina Beach and is

caught by the police but he is able to handle him only in fifty rupees. It is kind of 'MONEY SOLVE ALL THE PROBLEMS' in India. The constable shouts at Krish and grabs his arm with anger but when Krish pays him off everything gets over. Krish remembers, "I took out a fifty. He looked at me and Ananya. 'Warning' the cop said as he took the note."¹¹

In another instance Bhagat is amazed to see that money relaxes almost all the rules in the country. Krish goes to a government-approved liquor shop to buy wine where the rule is not to see the wine to person who is less than 25 but after paying 10 bucks extra per bottle all the rules went in vein.

Through Krish, Bhagat represents the voices of the youth who do not believe in social or economical disparities. India is one.

"These stupid biases and discrimination are the reason our country is so screwed up. It's Tamil first, Indian later. It has to end..... National anthem, national currency, national team - still, we won't marry our children outside our states. How can this intolerance be good for our country?"¹²

In this novel Chetan Bhagat beautifully deprecates the social and linguistic differences in the people belonging to different states and also their discrimination on the basis of their colour, face, language and styles.

References:

1. http://www.nytimes.com/2008/03/26/books/26_bhagat.html
2. http://www.Time.com/time/specials/packages/complete_list/0,29569,1984685,00.htm/
3. <http://www.fastcompany.com/most-creative-people/2011/chetan-bhagat-writer>

In this novel the younger generation (Krish and Ananya) is seen radical, creative, challenging, intellectual, adaptive and liberal while the older one (their parents) as submissive, conservative, conventional and stereotyped typically. But the elder one are not conservative but actually they are preservative in their point of view. They think they know the values better and they wish to preserve them. They don't wish to disturb life of Generation-Y deliberately, but they think what they are trying to do is right for the older and the younger generation from the cultural perspective. They believe that they are well care taker of their culture. The novel ends with the practical solution, better communication, young generation's initiative and lastly the elders support. Finally it concludes with how Krish and Ananya, the representatives of millennial generation paved the way to get married and to unite their families despite of all the adversities they travelled through inevitably.

Most important facet of this fiction is its relevance on the silver screen of Bollywood proved milestone for its growing success in year 2014 itself. Any writing when comes in movie form becomes memorable in the hearts of readers and audiences. Before this fiction Chetan's Five Points At Someone as Three Idiots had been on screen as a grand success and emerged as most popular movie of the decade. Congratulations to Chetan Bhagat.

-
4. Bhagat Chetan, 2 States, Rupa. co, New Delhi, 2009, PP-183, LL-22-23
 5. IbidPP-1, LL-8
 6. Ibid.....PP-1, LL-11-12
 7. Ibid.....PP-1, LL-4-7
 8. Ibid.....PP-26, LL-9-10
 9. Ibid.....PP-57,LL-2
 10. Ibid.....PP-167, LL-14-32
 11. Ibid.....PP-98, LL-19-20
 12. Ibid.....PP-102, LL-25-31

RESEARCH CHRONICLER